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Enhancing Software Quality in SMEs: A Holistic Approach to Testing Framework Development

Master's thesis in Computer science and engineering

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A testing framework to enhance software quality in SMEs

This chapter presents our proposed testing framework. It is based on the testing framework created by Argüello *et al.* [1]. Their framework has been revised and extended. The resulting framework has the same structure as the underlying one and is structured around a series of axes, each representing a critical aspect of the testing process. The original framework presented eight axes: Plan Definition, Affected Test Levels, Definition of Test Cases, Test Activities, Test Environment, Testing Tools, and Feedback. Four new axes were added for enhancement: Testing Knowledge, Code Quality, CI/CD Pipeline, and Developer Motivation.

Each axis is evaluated at three levels of testing maturity: No Implementation, Partial Implementation, and Full Implementation. This allows for a clear assessment of the current testing state. The axes outlined in the framework serve two fundamental objectives: diagnostic and directional, forming a comprehensive strategy for assessing and guiding software testing improvements. Three matrices are provided to support the previously named objectives. The first matrix, shown in 1.1, supports the diagnostic capability and describes the testing process aspects considered in the testing framework. Yet, the aspects are condensed to be easily followed. This matrix is complemented by a detailed description of each aspect. The other two matrices support the directional objective, outlining how to mature in each aspect. However, these two transition matrices have been partitioned so that each axis displays improvement activities directly after the axis explanation to facilitate the reading flow. However, if interested in studying the complete matrices, they are presented in Appendix A and B.

As in the original framework, it is recommended to approach the development of the axes in the order in which they are found in the matrices. This arrangement is deliberate, as they are organized according to the phase of the development process in which these testing activities are involved.

Two additional artifacts have been added to the framework. The first is a supplementary theory file, found in Appendix C, that aims to explain concepts raised in the framework that might not be known to every actor applying the framework. The theory file is, however, entirely supplementary and can be overlooked if the concepts in the framework are familiar. The framework refers to the theory file when the covered concepts are presented. The other artifact is an appendix of examples. This can be found in Appendix D.

In Section 1.1, the application process of the framework is presented. Following, Section 1.2 presents the different components of the framework. After the presenta-

tion of the framework, Section 1.3 motivates the axes and the changes and additions done to the original framework. The presentation and motivation of the framework are separated to allow for overlooking the motivation if only wanting advice on how to streamline an immature testing process of an SME.

1.1 Application Process

The framework implementation consists of five steps that should be applied in brief iterative cycles. The steps are Diagnosis, Detection of improvement activities, Contextual adjustment, Implementation of improvement activities, and Verification of results. Figure 1.1 provides a visual representation of the process.

During the diagnosis, the current state of the organization's testing process must be established. This is done by deciding the current level of each axis in the diagnosis matrix. Once the diagnosis is performed, the axes to be improved should be detected. It is recommended to start with the axes that are less developed and on areas that offer the most significant return on investment. However, the axes are presented in a deliberate order, which should be considered when addressing them. The next step of the framework implementation is the Contextual adjustment. It aims to tailor the recommendations to fit the company's specific context. During this step, companies should reflect on their available resources and existing processes. The considered resources could be available personnel, budget, and time for testing efforts. The processes adopted could be agile practices, among others. Based on the insights gained from reflecting on the company's available resources, constraints, and adopted processes, companies should then adapt the improvement recommendations to fit their unique context. This might involve scaling down larger initiatives to accommodate budget constraints or modifying practices to be more compatible with their workflow. The objective of reaching the highest level for all axes may not be immediately feasible for all companies; instead, it could be a long-term goal. To guide the Contextual Adjustment step, the following questions could be considered:

- What is the available budget for testing activities within the organization?
- What is the available personnel that can be allocated for testing activities, and to what extent (full-time, part-time, etc.)?
- What is the available time frame to introduce the chosen testing activities?
- What are the available resources to maintain the testing activities in the long term?
- How is the available testing knowledge within the company? Is the necessary expertise available within the organization?
- What are the current practices and processes within the organization, and how can they be integrated with the chosen testing activities?
- What are the benefits vs the cost of implementation of the chosen testing activities?

Only those activities that are considered reasonable to implement should be chosen. The implementation process continues with the implementation of the improvement activities for each axis. Finally, the results are verified, and the degree of evolution of the axis is re-measured using the diagnosis matrix, which effectively goes back to

the diagnosis step. This process is to be repeated iteratively until all the axes reach the desired level.

Figure 1.1: Illustration of the framework application process. The diagram is inspired by the original framework [1].

1.2 Presentation of Framework

Axis	No Implemen- tation	Partial Imple- mentation	Full Imple- mentation
Testing knowl- edge	Limited	High-level un- derstanding, not maintained	Continuously shared and maintained within the organization
Plan definition	No plan	Informal plan	Formal Plan. The plan is continuously maintained and evaluated.

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Affected test levels	No testing	Deliberate use of test levels. Mainly unit testing, some integration and system testing	Comprehensive unit, integration and system tests and higher level tests
Definition of test cases	No definition of test cases	High-level definition of test cases	Fully specified test cases
Test activities	No testing	Static or dynamic tests. Some testing techniques applied	Static and dynamic tests combined. Carefully selected testing techniques
Traceability	No traceability	Partial traceability	Full traceability
Test environment	No specific testing environment	Managed and controlled environment	Testing in a suitable environment
Testing tools	Non-specific tools	Specific tools for monitoring and executing tests	Extensive process automation
Code quality	Not considered or evaluated	Introduced guidelines	Full codebase adhere to guidelines
CI/CD pipeline	No tests included	Includes static and dynamic tests	Optimized tests
Feedback	No reports	Some internal and/or external defect reports	Extensive internal and external defect reports. Progress and process reports and activities
Developer motivation	No efforts have been made	Activities to enhance testing motivation have been introduced	Developers are motivated and recognized for testing activities

Table 1.1: Final proposed framework: Axis diagnostic matrix.

Testing Knowledge. Testing knowledge in this framework refers to the level of understanding of the different aspects and processes that software testing encompasses. This axis ensures knowledge in the area at the first maturity level, verifying that every developer possesses fundamental testing knowledge through simple means. This could be done by providing reports generated by trustworthy parties that suit the context, such as the testing guidelines provided by Microsoft: [2]. Continuing, the next maturity level encourages advancing the testing skills and knowledge sharing. This could be done by enrolling developers in testing courses of various ranges, from free online courses to academic or institutional sessions. The total improvement activities for each level are presented in Table 1.2.

In parallel with technical knowledge, an understanding of cognitive biases in relation to software testing is essential to be able to mitigate the phenomena [3]. This framework provides a condensed explanation of cognitive biases, found in Section C.7.1. The mentioned resource is encouraged to spread within the company for educational purposes. Finally, the distribution of knowledge within the organization could be achieved by, for example, providing communication channels assigned to discussing software testing or arranging simple presentations, engaging workshops, and conferences.

Testing knowledge	
Maturity stage	Improvement activities
From No Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include basic testing principles as well as the organizational approach regarding testing in the onboarding process • Provide simple resources to achieve fundamental testing knowledge • Emphasize unit testing • Clarify advantages of software testing
From Partial Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide courses in testing, with the possibility to advance in expertise level • Educate about cognitive biases that affect testing • Ensure fundamental testing skills before employment • Provide an opportunity to share knowledge with colleagues

Table 1.2: Evolution matrix for Testing knowledge.

Plan Definition. The Plan Definition axis involves activities that outline the test objectives and the strategies for reaching those objectives, ultimately resulting in

the creation of a straightforward and easy-to-follow testing process. This axis encompasses aspects such as the definition of clear Exit Criteria, which determines the set of conditions that should be met to consider the testing phase as concluded. An example of how an Exit Criteria could be formulated is shown in Appendix D. Other aspects included are clearly defining roles and responsibilities related to testing at the company and estimating time and resources destined for testing activities. Decisions about how the testing and development activities should be integrated should also be made. This could be, for example, deciding on a test-driven development process where the tests are written before the actual code or deciding on continuous collaboration between developers and testers by adopting agile methodologies.

The degree of evolution along this axis is determined by the level of detail and how the plan is communicated and formalized. In this context, formalization means that the testing process has been documented and distributed to all stakeholders. The transition suggestions are found in Table 1.3.

Ideally, test planning should begin early in the development process, simultaneously with obtaining requirements. The system's requirements should be clearly stated to enable traceability and monitoring of results. An example of system requirements is shown in Appendix D. The established testing process should be regularly maintained and evaluated to track its progress and be able to take corrective measures when necessary. Feedback from testing activities should be used to fine-tune the testing plan.

In the context of this axis the questions of when and where to test means making decisions on how often and under which circumstances test activities will take place. The answer to when to test could, for example, be: running the test suite every night or running them on every commit. The answer to where to test could be decisions on running the test suite locally or as part of a continuous integration pipeline. The specialized testing needs of the company refer to aspects of the software not directly related to a specific function or user action, such as performance, usability, reliability, and security.

When estimating the time needed for testing activities, the estimation technique Planning Poker is recommended. This technique consists of participants independently estimating tasks and simultaneously revealing their estimates. This process is done iterative until all participants have reached a consensus. It is recommended that companies balance testers' work schedules, allowing them to engage in other activities such as development.

Plan Definition	
Maturity stage	Improvement activities
From No Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Answer the questions: What do we test? What do we not test? And why do we do it? When do we test? Where do we test? • Define and communicate roles and responsibilities for testing activities. Assign someone responsible for the software testing • Integrate and coordinate testing activities with the development lifecycle • Define product requirements • Define Exit Criteria
From Partial Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Document the plan and distribute it to the development team and stakeholders • Make an estimated time budget required to carry out the test activities and add buffer time for testing activities • Generate a calendar with specific dates or in the context of each iteration • Estimate people and resources to carry out the planned activities. If possible, make a tentative assignment • Decide specialized testing needs at the company • Create opportunities for participatory decision-making • Hold retrospective meetings destined to maintain and evaluate the chosen testing process • Comprehend feedback from testing activities to fine-tune the testing plan • Follow up if product requirements have been fulfilled

Table 1.3: Evolution matrix for Plan definition.

Affected Test Levels. This axis addresses the question "What to test?" in terms of different test levels. If not familiar with the testing levels, read Section C.1 that swiftly covers the four most common testing levels; unit, integration, system, and acceptance. To effectively answer the primary question proposed by this axis, an analysis of the relevant modules to be tested in the code base should be undertaken. This involves determining which parts of the code are pertinent for testing at each

level. The different maturity levels cover the order in which the testing levels should be addressed. If starting from a case where test levels have not been considered at all, the first level to prioritize is unit tests. Then, integration and system test levels are naturally followed. Low-level testing allows defects to be addressed earlier in the testing process. The final maturity stage covers the top of the testing levels, as in acceptance tests. This should establish confidence in the product quality, ensuring its completeness and expected performance. The concrete steps for maturing are shown in Table 1.4.

In most cases, SMEs do not have a complete test suite. It is essential to prioritize testing time wisely when extending the suite. Encompassing a wide range of levels enables the early detection of deviations. To decide what tests should be performed at each level, it is suggested to analyze the existing test suite and identify gaps to fill.

Affected test levels	
Maturity stage	Improvement activities
From No Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyze the available test objects from the unit, integration and system-level test perspectives Identify the features to be tested from the previously analyzed test objects, as well as the conditions under which they will be tested A rule of thumb is to focus the density of tests in the order of the test pyramid, with most tests in the lower levels
From Partial Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyze the higher-level test objects, such as acceptance tests Identify the features to be tested in the previously added test levels.

Table 1.4: Evolution matrix for Affected test levels.

Definition of Test Cases. The axis Definition of Test Cases answers the question "How to test?". The involved activities extend from designing test cases to identifying input data, execution conditions, and expected results. This axis is considered to be at the lowest maturity level when no definition of test cases is generated, the middle level when high-level test cases have been identified, and at the highest level when the test cases have a complete specification of their inputs, execution conditions, and expected outcomes. In this context, a fully specified test case is defined as one that not only includes detailed information on the expected positive outcomes but also includes the negative outcomes and conditions which the software is not designed to handle or should explicitly fail under. The concrete steps for maturing

are shown in Table 1.5.

Generally, it is good practice to start with designing high-level test cases. These are expressed without concrete values for the input data and the expected results, also known as checklists. An example of a high-level test case is shown in Appendix D. High-level test cases can be reused in various stages of the software development life cycle and across different versions of the product. It should be noted that the generation of test cases also leads to the identification of other needs early on, such as the necessary infrastructure and tools.

It is recommended to apply a test specification technique when designing test cases since they provide a systematic approach to testing, helping to ensure test coverage and increasing the likelihood of identifying defects. Section C.3 delves into some established test specifications techniques, providing the bases for their implementation.

Ideally, each test case should be traceable bi-directionally to the specific test condition it addresses. This means starting from the test condition, often derived from requirements, tracing forward to the corresponding test cases designed to verify that the condition is met, and the same the other way around. When defining test cases, it is important to remember that each test case should be independent. This ensures consistency in the test process, mitigating the risk of cascading failures, where the failure of one test case affects the outcome of subsequent ones.

Another aspect to consider when generating test cases is the effects of cognitive biases. In particular, confirmation bias is a critical concern in software testing and is seriously detrimental to testing quality. One debiasing technique that mitigates this bias is explicitly asking developers to seek evidence of problems rather than the system working correctly. Another is asking developers to play devil's advocate and consider why the solution may be wrong. These direct questions can be added as a checklist.

Definition of test cases	
Maturity stage	Improvement activities
From No Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agree on a standard format for test case specification • Create high-level test cases. A checklist is often recommended as a first approximation

From Partial Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Choose appropriate test specification technique(s) to generate test cases • Utilize debasing techniques such as playing the devil's advocate • Generate test cases identifying: the possible input data, the execution conditions, and the expected results • Document the fully specified test cases for follow-up
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Table 1.5: Evolution matrix for Definition of test cases.

Test Activities. Software testing activities refer to the actions done in a testing process. Static and dynamic testing are the major broad categories within test activities. The fundamental difference between the categories is that dynamic testing encompasses code execution, whereas static testing does not. They complement each other by finding different types of defects, making it essential to perform both types of tests. Therefore, the axis's evolution targets the application of both test activities. The concrete steps for maturing are shown in table 1.6.

Automated test execution tools are suggested when performing dynamic tests. Some benefits are reduced repetitive manual work, time efficiency, greater consistency, objectivity, and repeatability. On the other hand, static testing relies on the manual evaluation of work products. However, static code analysis can be facilitated with the use of tools. Code reviews are a commonly practiced static test activity. Practicing code reviews enhances the quality of the software product while also fostering teamwork. An example of a clear guide to follow when performing code review activities can be found in Appendix D.

Within static and dynamic testing, different techniques can be applied. This framework will not cover the exhaustive list of testing techniques, but a few inspirational and commonly applied ones are; Risk-based testing, Regression testing, Sanity testing, Exploratory testing, Property-based testing, and Mutation testing. These are explained in Section C.2. Property-based testing is strongly dependent on a tool to assist the input generation. For the Java Framework, jqwik [4] is a commonly used and suggested tool. Mutation testing can also rely on testing tools. For Java, Pitest [5] is a common tool to use for mutation testing, and MutPy [6] for Python programmers. What technique and tool to choose depends on the context and present specialized testing needs.

Another testing activity that should be considered at the higher level of maturity is optimization techniques. Three common testing techniques in this regard are described in Section C.4, which all aim to reduce testing costs.

Test activities	
Maturity stage	Improvement activities
From No Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform static review tests, e.g., code reviews or inspections and walkthroughs • Perform exploratory dynamic tests manually • Consider basic testing techniques such as Regression testing and Sanity testing
From Partial Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform static analysis tests guided by tools such as source code analysis (examples are given in the Code Quality axis) • Automate dynamic tests • Consider more advanced testing techniques such as Search-based testing, Property-based testing, Mutation testing • Optimize tests

Table 1.6: Evolution matrix for Test activities.

Traceability. This axis involves the monitoring and control activities of the developed testing plan. Test monitoring refers to continuously evaluating the real progress against the predefined test plan. Meanwhile, test control refers to implementing necessary measures to achieve the goals outlined in the test plan. The degree of evolution across this axis is determined by the level of traceability between the test suite and the work products. To achieve the highest maturity level, requirements should be traced to the specific test case, highlighted in the transition matrix in Table 1.7.

Maintaining traceability during the entire testing process is crucial for successful test monitoring and control. Effective traceability enables the evaluation of test coverage. Furthermore, it enables the analysis of the impact of modifications and supplies data to appraise product quality, process capability, and advancement of business goals. To support the traceability of software testing efforts, test management tools such as QTest[7] and Zephyr[8] can be used. Such tools allow organizing test cases, planning test executions and tracking of results. They often integrate with requirements management and defect tracking tools such as Jira[9] to provide end-to-end traceability, maintaining a transparent and auditable trail from requirements to test cases and outcomes.

Traceability	
Maturity stage	Improvement activities
From No Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain traceability between test objects and test cases
From Partial Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add traceability between requirements and the test objects and test cases • Determine the coverage of the tests • Introduce test management tools

Table 1.7: Evolution matrix for Traceability.

Test Environment. The test environment axis covers the setup under which the tests are run. Various test categories can require different test environments. System-level testing should preferably be conducted in the system’s operating environment since detecting failures under those conditions becomes irrelevant if the testing environment differs significantly from the operating environment. However, due to resource constraints and practical limitations, it is often unfeasible to test in the production environment. Consequently, test environments should closely mirror real-world conditions as often as possible.

This particular axis aims to assess the level of suitability of the testing environment and how well it mirrors reality. The lowest maturity level represents the absence of an established testing environment. The next level is reached when a dedicated, incomplete environment for testing is available. This could be incomplete for various reasons, such as missing integrations or poorly defined data in the database. The final level is achieved when the testing environment fully mirrors the production environment. The transition matrix encouraging maturity of this axis is found in Table 1.8.

The highest maturity level includes a test harness, which contains all the information needed to run test cases in automated or integration testing. This could, for example, be configuration settings, managing test data, controlling the flow of test execution, and cleaning up after test execution. The final level also encourages the use of service virtualization. This is the practice of simulating dependencies and emulating the behavior of dependent systems to be able to remove constraints from the software under test. This enables testing earlier in the lifecycle since all of the software connections do not need to be available. Additionally, virtual services can save resources if the original components are expensive to interact with.

It is recommended to let a CI/CD pipeline be a part of the test environment by using it to trigger tests at different stages of the lifecycle. This is explained in greater detail in its axis further below.

A critical problem regarding the test environment is the risk of producing flaky tests. This means that the tests yield different results under the same conditions across runs. This could be caused by several testing nodes accessing and modifying the same database simultaneously. To mitigate this, mocking the database interactions for unit-level tests is a solution suggested in the final maturity matrix. Mocking means mimicking the interface of the actual dependencies but providing predefined responses to method calls, allowing developers to control the behavior of dependencies during testing.

Test environment	
Maturity stage	Improvement activities
From No Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build a test environment outside of the development and production environment • Prepare it with shared test data, where possible, that is similar to production data • Integrate triggering tests in the CI/CD pipeline
From Partial Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include in the test environment: test harness, service virtualization, simulators, and other necessary infrastructure elements • Prepare test data from production data and keep it up to date • Mock external dependencies as often as possible for lower-level tests

Table 1.8: Evolution matrix for Test environment.

Testing Tools. Numerous tools exist with the ambition to support different test activities. Overall, tools reduce the possibility of including errors. Testing tools can also support changing workflows by enforcing adherence to new guidelines and hindering old routines. In the meantime, only implementing a particular tool does not promise success. Every new tool introduced into the test process requires effort and proper management of people using the tool to achieve real and lasting benefits. It is important not to be tempted to apply complex tools only because they promise high results since it must be achievable to learn the tool given the resources. The maturity flow of this axis suggests when it is suitable to incorporate different types of tools in the testing process. The concrete steps for maturing in this axis are shown in Table 1.9.

Some examples of tools that support unit testing are JUnit[10] for Java and NUnit[11] for .NET languages. Together with GitHub Actions[12], unit tests could be automated if the repository is hosted on GitHub. The automation process is closely related to the CI/CD Pipeline. TeamCity[13] is an example of a tool that supports

testing at the delivery stage. A tool to assess the coverage of the test is suggested. For instance, JaCoCo[14] is a tool for Java development that outlines different kinds of code coverage, such as statement, branch, line, method, and class coverage. A suggested testing tool for integration tests is PostMan[15], a software facilitating integration testing by enabling API call testing. Jira[9] and GitHub Issues[16] are examples of tools that facilitate bug reporting and management of the test process.

Testing tools	
Maturity stage	Improvement activities
From No Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporate requirements and incident monitoring tools. As a first approximation, they can be carried in a spreadsheet, but it is advisable to use specific tools for this type of task • Incorporate test execution tools that allow them to be automated • Apply tools supporting unit testing
From Partial Implementation	<p>Incorporate tools for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • test management and test products • test design and implementation, including test cases, test procedures, and test data • execution and registration of tests • performance measurement and dynamic analysis • specialized testing needs such as security tests, portability, and accessibility

Table 1.9: Evolution matrix for Testing tools.

Code Quality. This axis aims to streamline the testing process by increasing the code quality of the code base. The transition suggestions are found in Table 1.10. The first transition establishes a shared perception of what defines the desired code quality and how to achieve it, as well as enforces application in the development routines. The final transition covers ensuring coherent code quality in the already existing code as well.

To increase code quality, adhering to code standards is essential. These include syntactical decisions such as naming conventions, formatting rules, code architecture, and design pattern guidelines. The large development ecosystems have their suggested conventions - to mention a few; .NET: [17], Java: [18], and Python: [19]. The specific conventions that suit the development context should be chosen. For example, if the system under development is an object-oriented product developed in the .NET framework, it would be suitable to follow the SOLID principles as well as .NET's coding style: [17]. Code standards are often dynamic and constantly

revised, so it is essential to stay updated. It is suggested to facilitate adherence to code standards by integrating a formatting tool. This could be integrated into the IDE. Again, what specific tools to use are context-dependent. As inspiration; ReSharper [20] developed by JeantBrains for C# and Pylint[21] for Python could be utilized. SonarQube[22] is another recommended static analysis tool that complies with several programming languages. SonarQube can help detect other code quality issues, such as code smells and complexity (described in Section C.8).

Code quality	
Maturity stage	Improvement activities
From No Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chose code standard(s) to follow and establish a routine for staying updated with the guidelines (suggestion: workshop once a year) • Introduce automated tools for continuous assessment of code quality • Integrate the code quality aspects to code reviews • Communicate and educate the importance of modular code • Pair programming is encouraged • Comment the code
From Partial Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do a full scan of the code base and fix existing code quality issues. This could be a good opportunity for someone with lower domain expertise or experience at the company to familiarize themselves with the code base (e.g., a summer job or a project for a new employee) • The code quality of every new change should be evaluated to meet the code quality guidelines

Table 1.10: Evolution matrix for Code quality.

CI/CD Pipeline. This axis defines how to integrate testing into an existing CI/CD pipeline. It is generically formulated since a pipeline is highly dependent on the context, as in what tools and frameworks are applied in the current project. The goal of the maturity in this axis is to transition into a CI/CD pipeline where optimized testing is seamlessly integrated through automated processes. Table 1.11 presents the improvement activities for each of the three maturity stages.

The No Implementation level assumes a basic production environment; a version control system, a platform for hosting the repository, and a deployment stage, but without any testing activities. If a pipeline is not set up, it is recommended to

browse the internet to see what solutions fit the context. For example, if working with GitHub, numerous guides exist provided by the engaged community. Among others is this blog post: [23].

A development pipeline, including tests, can be of various ranges, and the comprehensiveness often reflects the execution time. However, the more rigorous testing in the pipeline, the higher the chance of catching faults, desirably as early as possible. Automated tools are suggested because they make the testing activities less disruptive, leaving the execution time not to affect the developer so much. For example, SonarQube, mentioned in the Code Quality axis, can be integrated seamlessly to be run on every commit if the repository is cloud-based, with the use of SonarCloud [24]. Running linters can also be automatically triggered in the CI/CD pipeline.

CI/CD pipeline	
Maturity stage	Improvement activities
From No Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up a pre-commit or pre-push command that runs formatting and simple tests • Create a build script in the repository that states which set of tests should be run on every commit/push. Update the chosen set regularly • Integrate static code analysis tools for performing code quality checks • Create a build script for the deployment including what tests to run at this stage
From Partial Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prioritize the order of the test cases in the build scripts • Perform risk assessment and run the critical first • Examine the different tests to not cover redundant tests • Ensure to not run the same tests in several build scripts if not needed

Table 1.11: Evolution matrix for CI/CD pipeline.

Feedback. There are different types of feedback involved in the testing process, including internal and external reports. Internal feedback includes information about when a test level is completed, how the testing is progressing, results from code reviews and test execution, and how well the tests cover the software under test. Also, providing feedback on the process and its activities is important. It can contribute to building good relationships since feedback creates a space for dialogue that allows visibility of progress and leads to continuous improvement. External feedback

includes, among others, feedback from users, acceptance testing, and bug reports. Many of the internal and external reports can be elicited from metric-based tools. Some examples are code coverage tools (for example JaCoCo [14], test execution tools (for example Resharper [20]) and testing management tools (e.g., Jira [9]).

For this axis to provide value to the company, the feedback reports must be carefully considered as the initialization for improvement actions. Involving feedback in the development lifecycle adds administrative overhead, but it can also be added with small means. Therefore, many of the improvement activities suggested rely on automation.

The maturity in this axis is based on how many aspects of the process are evaluated with feedback. The transition matrix is found in Table 1.12. The No Implementation level covers the scenario when no feedback reports are provided. The second maturity level includes some internal and/or external reports, whereas the final maturity level also incorporates process and progress evaluation. Reports in this axis refer to any artifact containing feedback results and do not explicitly mean a report in paper format.

Feedback	
Maturity stage	Improvement activities
From No Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish metrics, such as code coverage, testing time, and number of failures • Integrate tools for extracting the metrics • Gather feedback from users • Keep a count of the test cases executed, the results obtained, and the defects reported
From Partial Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generate progress reports to evaluate the process of testing • Allow interested parties to provide feedback about the quality achieved and priorities for future releases

Table 1.12: Evolution matrix for Feedback.

Developer Motivation. The axis Developer Motivation highlights the factors influencing human motivation to perform software testing. This encompasses both motivational and de-motivational factors as well as proposed strategies to increase motivation.

The degree of maturity evolution across this axis is determined by the efforts made to stimulate and motivate software developers to test. The company is considered at the lowest level when no effort has been made to motivate the developers to test. The company is considered at the intermediate level when activities to enhance testing

motivation have been consciously introduced. This indicates that motivation has been acknowledged as a relevant aspect of the testing process. The highest level is determined by developers feeling motivated and recognized for testing activities. Concrete steps to reach a higher maturity level are displayed in Table 1.13.

To increase motivation it is recommended to combine testing responsibilities with development activities. In companies with a designated testing department, the testers should be involved during the entire development process and not only at the end. Recognition has a clear role in software professionals' motivation toward testing activities. Making developers feel recognized can be achieved by actively giving positive feedback related to software activities and by working towards raising the status of testing at the company. Testing activities should be considered as crucial as development activities. Finding bugs should be encouraged for testers to feel motivated to do their job. If testers feel unpopular when opening critical defects, they could become reluctant even if it is a severe defect [25].

Developer motivation	
Maturity stage	Improvement activities
From No Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the testing status at the company • Combine testing responsibilities with development activities • Ensure a variety of engaging and challenging tasks • Encourage a good relationship with management and colleagues • Set aside time destined for only testing activities • Ensure the testing environment holds a high-quality • Provide a clear testing strategy to follow • Provide clear test examples to follow
From Partial Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduce ways to provide positive feedback when discovering faults • Ensure active influence in decisions concerning the testing process • Make use of code quality metrics • Adopt pair programming practices

Table 1.13: Evolution matrix for Developer motivation.

1.3 Motivation of Framework

The framework in general is motivated by both the focused literature review as well as the analysis of the participatory company. The literature highlights the importance of a high-quality test suite since it facilitates the evolvment and maintenance of the software [26]. The analysis of the company clearly expressed a need for guidelines regarding the testing process to manifest confidence in the codebase, especially when the codebase grows rapidly.

The original framework has been extended with new aspects found to be essential for more a complete testing framework, and some elements have been removed when not supported by literature or the company analysis. The aspects were reformulated when objectives were not clearly communicated, and several factors were explained more concretely with examples, with the ambition to facilitate easy adoption of the framework for industrial companies. However, the original framework generally received positive feedback and was concluded to be easily followed, which is why components were edited with caution. The format of the framework was kept due to the feedback about its simplicity and practicality. The concrete changes performed on the framework matrices are shown in a color-coded version highlighting the revisions in Appendix E.

Examples of tools, processes, and relevant literature were added to the framework to inspire companies with little experience in testing. Additionally, [3] states that techniques can often debias tasks faster than awareness of the human can, which makes it a fast track to take in parallel with educating the developers about potential biases.

The following section is organized as follows: First, the refinement of the implementation process is motivated. Then, all axes are motivated in the order they are presented in the framework.

1.3.1 Contextual Adjustment

When attempting to implement Test Process Improvement (TPI) models, SMEs encounter distinct challenges that differ from those larger organizations face. SMEs are often limited by resources in terms of finance, available time, and skilled personnel within specific areas, such as software testing. These limitations can affect their ability to implement and maintain rigorous testing processes [27]. Additionally, significant variability exists within the companies that fit the SME definition, encompassing companies with up to 250 employees. The specific processes utilized at the company can vary considerably, as one organization can operate in an agile environment while others use the waterfall approach.

In order to address the mentioned difficulties and the great diversity within the SME landscape, it is fundamental that companies adjust to the models as necessary to fit their unique context and constraints. The Contextual Adjustment step was added to the original implementation process to facilitate a pragmatic and tailored approach to the proposed framework. This step ensures that the proposed improvements are not only theoretically sound but also practically viable, taking into account the company's specific operational environment, resources, workflow methodologies,

and strategic goals. In essence, the Contextual Adjustment step aims to make the framework not just a set of best practices but a dynamic tool that respects the unique nature of each organization, facilitating a more thoughtful and effective implementation of software testing improvements.

1.3.2 Testing knowledge

Possessing knowledge about software testing is fundamental to being able to perform any testing activities. Without understanding the advantages of testing or the drawbacks of neglecting it, spending resources on testing activities is unreasonable. Therefore, this aspect is added to the framework, placing it in the beginning to serve as a foundation for the framework. Ng *et al.* [28] presents that the primary factor hindering organizations from adopting software testing methodologies is the lack of testing knowledge. Toroi *et al.* [29] agrees and emphasizes that developers need more testing expertise. Kituyin and Amulen [27] points out lack of competence in specific software engineering areas as a common prohibitive factor when applying test process improvement in SME environments. These are only some example studies that highlight the importance of testing knowledge. Fraser and Straubinger [26] highlight how knowing the significance of testing activities can motivate developers to perform software testing. The focus on unit testing knowledge is because of several resources highlighting the importance of unit testing, among others Toroi *et al.* [29] and Torkar and Mankefors-Christiernin [30]. Torkar and Mankefors-Christiernin explain that unit testing is crucial since it ensures a stable foundation in the code if appropriately done, hindering errors from propagating throughout the software. The suggestion about testing courses as a solution to achieve testing expertise is inspired by [26] that highlights how developers who have completed software testing courses see the benefits of software testing and are generally more motivated to perform software testing. Finally, education about cognitive biases is suggested since [3] and [31] highlight how knowledge about biases serves as a mitigation to the bias.

1.3.3 Plan Definition

The main structure and most of the recommendations included in the Plan Definition axis were kept as presented in the original framework. This axis's importance was supported by the literature and interviews conducted at the company. During the interviews, the need to decide on testing procedures and communicate them through the organization was clearly expressed. There was a general uncertainty about the testing process, resulting in feeling unsure about the quality of the code. Straubinger and Fraser present a solution by stating that thorough testing gives developers peace of mind, providing a feeling of security [26]. This was supported during the interviews where developers expressed they would feel safer if more testing was introduced at the company.

Even though the plan definition axis was deemed appropriate in the original framework, several aspects were added to enhance the activities. Some of the added aspects have their foundation in the current research in Behavioral Software engineering, considering how human aspects affect the planning process. Participatory

decision-making and retrospective meetings were recommended since they have been shown to ameliorate the effects of availability bias on effort estimation and decision-making [3]. It has also been shown that decision-makers struggle to adjust to new or changed environments because they are anchored on their outdated understanding of the context [3]. The practice of retrospective meetings can also reduce this difficulty. The interviews revealed a lack of space to bring up ideas for improvements and reconsider previous decisions. This problem is also tackled by the recommendations on creating opportunities for participatory decision-making, as well as defining clear roles and responsibilities for the testing process.

Another aspect added was the recommendation to use the estimation technique Planning Poker when estimating a time budget for testing activities since it has been shown to mitigate anchoring and adjustment biases [3].

Furthermore, the recommendation to formulate a clear Exit Criteria was made, given that the lack of specific quality goals can result in misguided assumptions about code quality and the overall necessity of testing [26]. It was also recommended to encourage testing activities early in the development process since this contributes to decreasing testing costs and improving efficiency [32]. Introducing traceability early on was recommended since it will ensure that all requirements are covered when applying the defined testing process, facilitating the identification of any missing or incomplete tests [33]. Another recommendation is to combine testing and development activities since individuals who are not only involved in testing activities have been shown to have lower confirmation bias, making them better testers [34]. Concerns about when and where to test were revealed during the interviews. These aspects were not included in the original framework but were considered necessary. Therefore, "When do we test?" and "Where do we test?" were added.

The findings in the literature revealed a common problem in small organizations: employees exhibit a high degree of self-trust and place significant emphasis on personal responsibility [27]. This phenomenon can manifest to the extent of employees feeling exempt from adhering to rules. This characteristic was also present in the analyzed company, where much emphasis was put on personal responsibility. The literature also indicates the common existence of flat organizational hierarchies in SME environments, where roles and responsibilities are often unclear. This characteristic was also observed at the participatory company, where testing responsibilities were not assigned to any specific person. These issues are yet another reason for creating a clear testing plan.

1.3.4 Affected Test Levels

This axis is only slightly adjusted compared to the original framework. This is because this study's findings align with this aspect in the original framework, strengthening this axis even further. Since testing on different levels targets different potential problems, this is a valid axis to include. The interviews at the participatory company highlighted that they miss testing on some levels, for example, testing API calls, which also argues the importance of including a reminder about different testing levels in a complete framework. The original framework included suggestions

about specialized testing needs and considered prioritization of test cases. These two suggestions were removed from this axis since they were assessed to belong to other axes instead; Plan Definition and Test Activities, respectively.

A rule of thumb on how to prioritize the amount of testing performed on each level was added to the transition matrix from No Implementation level. This was because the literature review showed that lower-level testing is the fundamental core of testing and should be carried out in the early stages of testing [30]. It was also adjusted to include integration tests at the Partial Implementation level since the original framework received feedback from an expert group that integration tests should be carried out in conjunction with the early unit tests.

1.3.5 Definition of Test Cases

The Definition of Test Cases axis was also to a large extent kept as in the original framework. Nevertheless, some recommendations were added to enhance the existing framework. Once again, research in the field of BSE and considerations of how human aspects affect the testing process stand as the foundation for many of the changes introduced in this axis.

There is strong evidence of confirmation bias among software developers regardless of their level of expertise [31]. This bias explains the tendency among software testers to create and execute test cases that affirm the anticipated functioning of the program rather than conducting tests that uncover defects [3]. To mitigate this bias, the concept of a fully specified test case was introduced. This recommendation was based on the discoveries of the paper "Analyses of factors related to positive test bias in Software Testing" [31]. This study states that the effects of confirmation bias appear to be mitigated by using more complete specifications. Using debiasing techniques, such as playing devil's advocate, was recommended based on the findings in the paper "Cognitive Biases in Software Engineering: A Systematic Mapping Study" [3]. This paper recommends using direct questions through a checklist to mitigate overconfidence and optimism bias. These recommendations align with trying to break the system instead of trying to write perfect test cases, which is also encouraged in the mentioned study. The recommendation of agreeing on a standard format for test specification early on was also added, given that a standard format makes test cases reusable and self-sufficient [29].

1.3.6 Test Activities

This axis was extended with new aspects compared to the original framework. The original framework only highlighted static and dynamic testing, which are fundamental test activities but are not hands-on themselves. This framework extends the suggestion by including examples of appropriate testing techniques to apply in the testing activities to inspire more concrete activities. The interviews highlighted the importance of regression testing, which is why it was added to the first transition matrix. Risk-based testing was also added in the first transition matrix because of the incitement provided by the ISO/IEC/IEEE standard [35]. Mutation testing was included since the literature review highlighted that developers tend to desire

feedback on how good their tests are [30]. Exploratory testing was added in the first transition matrix since it is easy to conduct and is, therefore, a good start for testing. However, this methodology is prone to human biases, and the tester could miss important aspects, which is why we suggest several other techniques as well, with the ambition that the techniques can compensate for each other's limitations.

1.3.7 Traceability

The traceability axis was kept as in the original framework, and no considerable changes were deemed necessary. The existing literature supports the critical role of traceability in software maintenance and evolution activities. The literature reveals that companies utilizing traceability were more efficient in completing maintenance tasks and generated more accurate solutions. This evidence suggests that traceability can reduce the workload associated with maintenance activities and enhance the overall quality of software maintenance [36].

1.3.8 Test Environment

This axis was extended compared to the original one. It is a critical axis to include since a testing environment is fundamental for executing tests on a broader scale and to be able to automate them in the shared repository. Test harness and service virtualization were explained since these concepts are not guaranteed to be understood by the intended reader, which was revealed during the company workshop. The company interviews highlighted the problem of flaky tests, which is why the axis was extended with a suggestion about mocking external dependencies, such as a test database. It was added that the database should be shared since [29] pinpoints this to be valuable since several developers have the same needs regarding testing data. A hint about integrating tests into the CI/CD pipeline was added since automation is considered a critical part of the test environment, according to the literature. More elaborated motivations about automation and CI/CD pipelines are presented in Section 1.3.11.

1.3.9 Testing Tools

Argüello *et al.* [1] highlight several benefits of testing tools: they improve the efficiency of testing activities by automating the manual, repetitive, or resource-intensive tasks (for example, running regression tests); they support manual testing activities throughout the testing process; increase the reliability of tests; they improve quality by allowing more consistent testing and a higher level of defect reproducibility. Additionally, the literature review suggested keeping the tools simple and easy to learn [30] [29], which is why the axis was extended with this proposal. Toroi *et al.* [29] also pinpoints that proper management of people is important when applying tools, which is why it is addressed in the framework. Due to the emphasis on unit testing in the literature, tools for automation of unit testing were explicitly brought up in the first transition matrix. Tools supporting different types of code coverage were discussed in the axis to shed light onto different aspects that indicate

how well the tests cover the product under test since this was concluded a desire in Torkar and S. Mankefors-Christiernin's study [30].

1.3.10 Code Quality

The code quality directly influences the codebase's testability, and poor code quality increases testing costs. Code quality contributes to the code's comprehensibility, a fundamental factor for testing activities. Therefore, code quality should be considered when streamlining a testing process and was added as an axis in the framework. Fraser and Straubinger [26] highlight that a common opinion among developers is that they are reluctant to test other developers' code since it can be hard to understand someone else's code. Similarly, the company interviews revealed that developers found it hard to comprehend the code, and the company has no clearly communicated code style. This is why the framework forces standardization of code style in the first maturity transition. Tools are suggested since they can help the developer follow code standards. Pair programming is recommended since experimental results made by Williams *et al.* [37] indicate that it achieves higher code quality, no matter the expertise level of the developer. The importance of modular code was explicitly added since the interviews at the participatory company revealed that the testing was prohibited because of monolithic code architecture.

1.3.11 CI/CD Pipeline

This axis was added to the framework since the literature and the participating company highlight the importance of making testing as close to non-events as possible, with automation being a trending topic of interest. The interviews revealed that developers at the company do not want to take time and effort from development to testing, which encourages leaving the testing to the CI/CD pipeline. Literature about motivation among developers explicitly encourages integrating tests into the pipeline since many developers think testing is tedious and challenging to do manually [26], causing it to decrease work satisfaction. Kituyin and Amulen [27] also mentioned the difficulties balancing improvement efforts and ongoing development activities in SME environments. Automating the testing process can contribute to alleviating these difficulties. Literature also highlights how code quality and DevOps are closely related [38], leaving DevOps to be closely related to testing since code quality and testing are intertwined. CI/CD pipelines are practices within the DevOps framework, which makes it an approach to engage with code quality.

The analysis at the company resulted in an understanding that test execution time is a critical factor. To target this, optimization techniques are (again) encouraged to shrink the test suite execution time. The advice to ensure that the same tests do not run multiple times, if not having arguments for it, was also added because of the company analysis since this was a contributing factor to the company's test execution time. Additionally, interviews at the company led to the addition of regularly updating the set of tests selected for automation. This aims to keep the tests updated with the evolution of the code base.

1.3.12 Feedback

The Feedback axis was highly inspired by the original framework since it received no constructive feedback. However, it was reformulated to address the problems of SMEs more explicitly. More concrete actions are suggested in this extended framework instead of the fairly abstract ones provided by the original framework. For example, "Generate reports of internal defect" was reformulated into two hands-on steps; 1) "Establish metrics, such as code coverage and number of failures" and 2) "Integrate tools or procedures for extracting the metrics". This was done based on the literature review showing how SMEs struggle to apply abstract guidelines. Additionally, it was explicitly addressed in the description of the axis that the term "reports" does not necessarily mean reports in paper format. This was done since using the word without explanation leaves the interpretation to the ambiguity of the word, and the literature review highlighted how extensively paper format reports do not suit SMEs since they do not have the resources to manage a lot of extensive documents.

The middle maturity level was adjusted to include external reports, given the evidence of the participating company's substantial integration of customer feedback juxtaposed with its limited incorporation of internal feedback. Therefore, it was concluded that it is possible to practice external reports without being at the top maturity level.

1.3.13 Developer Motivation

Motivation has been reported to have a pivotal impact on productivity and software quality management. However, motivation continues to be undervalued [39]. Low motivation can result in inadequate testing and the overlooking of software flaws [40]. This perspective is corroborated by Shah *et al.* [41], showing that testing quality is significantly influenced by the motivation of testers and the recognition of their testing efforts. Given the importance of motivation for successful testing activities, the axis developer motivation was added to the framework.

Many of the recommendations proposed in this axis aim to increase recognition of testing efforts. Recognition is pivotal when applying SPI strategies [27]. Straubinger and Fraser found in their study "A Survey on What Developers Think About Testing" [26] that nearly 60% of participants would test more if better recognized. Working towards increasing the status of testing activities and providing positive feedback when failures are reported are recommended in the framework as impact strategies to offer recognition.

The study "Challenges and strategies for motivating software testing personnel" [25] proposed a series of motivational factors in software testing that were added as recommendations in this framework. Recommendations such as combining testing responsibilities with development, encouraging good relationships between management and colleagues, and ensuring various engaging and challenging tasks were all found to be contributing factors to developer motivation. Pair programming is considered an enjoyable activity for both student and professional programmers, improving their job satisfaction and overall confidence in their work [37]. Given the advantages of pair programming, this practice is also recommended in this frame-

work to increase motivation.

Recommendations aimed to facilitate the testing efforts were also added to the framework with the ambition to increase developer motivation. A need to reduce the threshold for testing was expressed during the interviews. Some of the suggestions made to achieve this were providing test examples to follow and having a test strategy defining what and how to test. Supporting this, findings in the literature point out that many developers would engage more in testing if it were technically easier [26]. The utilization of code quality metrics was also considered a motivational factor in the testing process, given that motivation to test can be influenced by the awareness of the quality of the code [26]. The recommendation to set aside time destined for testing activities was also supported by the literature as a motivational factor. It was corroborated during the workshop session when a group of the participants reflected on how they would disregard testing if they already felt stressed by development work. Setting specific time aside for testing was considered an important measure.

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A

Evolution matrix from No Implementation level

Axis	Improvement activities
Testing knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Include basic testing principles as well as the organizational approach regarding testing in the onboarding process• Provide simple resources to achieve fundamental testing knowledge• Emphasize unit testing• Clarify advantages of software testing
Plan definition	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Answer the questions: What do we test? What do we not test? And why do we do it? When do we test? Where do we test?• Define and communicate roles and responsibilities for testing activities. Assign someone responsible for the software testing• Integrate and coordinate testing activities with the development lifecycle• Define product requirements• Define exit criteria
Affected test levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Analyze the available test objects from the unit, integration and system-level test perspectives• Identify the features to be tested from the previously analyzed test objects, as well as the conditions under which they will be tested• A rule of thumb is to focus the density of tests in the order of the test pyramid, with most tests in the lower levels

A. Evolution matrix from No Implementation level

Definition of test cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Agree on a standard format for test case specification• Create high-level test cases. A checklist is often recommended as a first approximation
Test activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Perform static review tests, e.g., code reviews or inspections and walkthroughs• Perform exploratory dynamic tests manually• Consider basic testing techniques such as Regression testing and Sanity testing
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Maintain traceability between test objects and test cases
Test environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Build a test environment outside of the development and production environment• Prepare it with shared test data, where possible, that is similar to production data• Integrate triggering tests in the CI/CD pipeline
Testing tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Incorporate requirements and incident monitoring tools. As a first approximation, they can be carried in a spreadsheet, but it is advisable to use specific tools for this type of task• Incorporate test execution tools that allow them to be automated• Apply tools supporting unit testing
Code quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Chose code standard(s) to follow and establish a routine for staying updated with the guidelines (suggestion: workshop once a year)• Introduce automated tools for assessing code quality• Integrate the code quality aspects to code reviews• Communicate and educate the importance of modular code• Pair programming is encouraged• Comment the code

A. Evolution matrix from No Implementation level

CI/CD pipeline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up a pre-commit command that runs formatting and simple tests • Create a build script in the repository that states which set of tests should be run on every commit/push. Update the chosen set regularly • Integrate static code analysis tools for performing code quality checks • Create a build script for the deployment including what tests to run at this stage
Feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish metrics, such as code coverage, testing time, and number of failures • Integrate tools for extracting the metrics • Gather feedback from users • Keep a count of the test cases executed, the results obtained, and the defects reported
Developer motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the testing status at the company • Combine testing responsibilities with development activities • Ensure a variety of engaging and challenging tasks • Encourage a good relationship with management and colleagues • Set aside time destined for only testing activities • Ensure the testing environment holds a high quality • Provide a clear testing strategy to follow • Provide clear test examples to follow

Table A.1: Final proposed framework: Evolution matrix from No Implementation level.

B

Evolution matrix from Partial Implementation level

Axis	Improvement activities
Testing knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Provide courses in testing, with the possibility to advance in expertise level• Educate about cognitive biases that affect testing• Ensure fundamental testing skills before employment• Provide an opportunity to share knowledge with colleagues
Plan definition	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Document the plan and distribute it to the development team and stakeholders• Make an estimated time budget required to carry out the test activities and add buffer time for testing activities• Generate a calendar with specific dates or in the context of each iteration• Estimate people and resources to carry out the planned activities. If possible, make a tentative assignment• Decide specialized testing needs at the company• Create opportunities for participatory decision-making• Hold retrospective meetings destined to maintain and evaluate the chosen testing process• Comprehend feedback from testing activities to fine-tune the testing plan• Follow up if product requirements have been fulfilled
Affected test levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Analyze the higher-level test objects, such as acceptance tests• Identify the features to be tested in the previously added test levels

B. Evolution matrix from Partial Implementation level

<p>Definition of test cases</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Choose appropriate test specification technique(s) to generate test cases • Utilize debasing techniques such as playing the devil’s advocate. • Generate test cases identifying: the possible input data, the execution conditions, and the expected results. • Document the fully specified test cases for follow-up
<p>Test activities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform static analysis tests guided by tools such as source code analysis (examples are given in the Code Quality axis) • Automate dynamic tests • Consider more advanced testing techniques such as Search-based testing, Property-based testing, Mutation testing • Optimize tests
<p>Traceability</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add traceability between requirements and the test objects and test cases • Determine the coverage of the tests • Introduce test management tools
<p>Test environment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include in the test environment: test harness, service virtualization, simulators, and other necessary infrastructure elements • Prepare test data from production data and keep it up to date • Mock external dependencies as often as possible for lower-level tests
<p>Testing tools</p>	<p>Incorporate tools for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • test management and test products • test design and implementation, including test cases, test procedures, and test data • execution and registration of tests • performance measurement and dynamic analysis • specialized testing needs such as security tests, portability, and accessibility

B. Evolution matrix from Partial Implementation level

Code quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Do a full scan of the code base and fix existing code quality issues. This could be a good opportunity for someone with lower domain expertise or experience at the company to familiarize themselves with the code base (e.g., a summer job or a project for a new employee)• The code quality of every new change should be evaluated to meet the code quality guidelines
CI/CD pipeline	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Prioritize the order of the test cases in the build scripts• Perform risk assessment and run the critical first• Examine the different tests to not cover redundant tests• Ensure to not run the same tests in several build scripts if not needed
Feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Generate progress reports to evaluate the process of the testing• Allow interested parties to provide feedback about the quality achieved and priorities for future releases
Developer motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Introduce ways to provide positive feedback when discovering faults• Ensure active influence in decisions concerning the testing process• Make use of code quality metrics• Adopt pair programming practices

Table B.1: Final proposed framework: Evolution matrix from Partial Implementation level.

C

Theory

Many of the concepts explained in this appendix are based on the broadly accepted ISO/IEC/IEEE 29119 standard [35]. Using the standard as the foundation of theory ensures high quality due to the nature of international standards provided by experts in the field. If the information or concepts presented are based on other resources, those are explicitly cited in the text.

C.1 Levels of Testing

It is possible to test software on different levels. Each level has a subsequent purpose that aims to target certain risks. The generally acknowledged hierarchy of levels is unit testing, integration testing, system testing, and acceptance testing. It is common to model the levels as a pyramid to showcase how the levels are the foundation of each other, see Figure C.1. The pyramid also showcases how the number of test cases generally decreases as advancing in the levels.

Unit testing is the lowest level and aims to test a small isolated piece of code at the time, for example, a method or class. The goal is to verify the specific functionality of the unit under test, without any dependencies to other parts of the code. Torkar and Mankefors-Christiernin [30] highlights that unit testing is often considered crucial at the beginning of software testing since it hinders faults from propagating to the other levels. To achieve isolated units of code, software mocking can be used. Mocking means mimicking the interface of the real dependencies but providing predefined responses to method calls, allowing developers to control the behavior of these dependencies during testing. If not using mocking, and

rather letting different components of the code interact during the test, the test is on the integration level. The objective of this test level is to verify that the interactions between components are working correctly. On the integration testing level, it is still fairly easy to correct faults as the tests are positioned close to the artifacts. When moving upwards in the pyramid, the artifacts are combined and more complex which makes it more difficult to detect the fault.

System tests deviate from integration tests as they concern the system outcome, and do not cover the specific implementation of components. This means that system tests can also involve API calls to another source, which makes the faults

Figure C.1: The "testing pyramid".

more difficult to correct for the developer alone. However, these kinds of tests are important as they are more realistic than the previous levels, yet still possible to perform from the developer site. The testing pyramid is completed with Acceptance testing, which aims to test the system in its intended context. This is made by end users, and is thereby not possible to automate, which makes this an expensive, yet vital test.

C.2 Testing Techniques

There exist numerous techniques aiming to facilitate the process of software testing. What they have in common is in general that they are methodologies expressed abstractly and generically, making it possible to apply them in various contexts. Below, some acknowledged testing techniques are explained. What these have in common is the shared goal of enhancing the effectiveness of testing. Some focus on streamlining the testing process (Regression Testing, Sanity testing), others on identifying defects (Exploratory testing, Property-based testing, Risk-based testing), and one focuses on the quality of the test cases (Mutation testing). The next section, Section C.3, delves deeper into the area of deriving test cases by exploring test specification techniques.

Regression Testing refers to retesting software after modifications. The aim is to verify the original behavior of the software so that the modification does not intrude on existing functionality or introduce new issues. It is a powerful approach to catch unintended introduced side effects. To achieve this, it is common to specify a regression test suite that exercises the most important functions without testing in detail. It is advised to have tests of different levels in the regression suit. Regression tests could be automatically triggered by every commit through the Continuous Integration (CI) pipeline, which is further described in Section C.5. [42]

Sanity Testing extends regression testing, by adding initial checks before the comprehensive regression testing is executed, to be able to stop the build before the full suite is executed. Sanity testing can also be conducted in other stages of the software lifecycle, such as before a demo or before acceptance testing by the user. The aim is to run a few critical tests to ensure fundamental functionality. [43]

Exploratory Testing is an experience-based test technique. In general, these are informal and include little planning, which makes them simple to conduct. However, it is difficult to measure the coverage of an experience-based test technique since the full set to test must not be defined. Exploratory testing means that testers interact with the product creatively, finding out what it can do and not, and potentially revealing bugs or flaws. The tester bases the behavior on existing experience and knowledge about user behavior and common types of failure. [42]

Property-based Testing advances the lower level of testing by allowing a tool to generate random inputs for the test case and assert that the input obeys a certain property, instead of verifying a specific output as many traditional testing techniques

would do. The tool generates inputs with the ambition to try to find values that break the property, to reveal faults in the code. The explanation of this technique is based on the conference paper [44] provided by Karlsson *et al.* They give a clarifying example to illustrate property-based testing:

"Imagine that we test a search function. The search function requires a search string as input and returns a list of items that match the search string. Instead of using a predefined search string with a predefined outcome, we instead use a string generator for the input string and formulate the invariant properties of the resulting list of items. Such properties include (1) the name of the resulting entities should always contain the search string as a substring in their name (2) the returned entities should always conform to a given format and (3) the function should always return a successful result, i.e., not crash. "

Risk-based Testing is a testing technique where the activities performed are based on the analyzed risk of performing, or not performing, the test. Risks can belong to either the product or the project. Potential risks must first be identified, and then the potential impact and likelihood of those are analyzed. This forms a perception of the situation at hand, and based on the perception an action is decided. A common driver in this testing technique is the risk that the product does not meet the stakeholder demand. The ISO/IEC/IEEE standard [35] recommends risk-based testing as the approach to strategies and management testing.

A testing technique that rather tests the quality of the tests is **mutation testing**. The theory in this paragraph is based on Su *et al.*'s conference paper [45]. The core of mutation testing is that the developer actively inserts a bug in the code, and then runs the test connected to it to verify that the test reveals the fault. If the fault is not revealed, the test case should be revised. To guide how to insert a bug in the code, mutant operators assist. A mutant operator is a guideline for how to modify a statement in the code into a faulty statement. The operators are defined with the target to simulate acknowledged programming errors. There exist numerous mutant operators. One example is to replace the operator `>` with `>=`. Many others are shown on the webpage [46] that hosts the mutation testing tool Pitest [5] for the Java framework.

C.3 Test specification techniques

Test specification techniques are methods used to derive and select test cases. These techniques can be broadly categorized into Specification-based testing and Code-based testing. The first category includes techniques that use the program requirements as testing input, while the second category can be explained as techniques that use the source code to guide the testing activities. These techniques complement each other and both should be used in order to find a complete test suite. The following sections will delve deeper into some well-known test specification techniques. The concepts explained are based on Aniche's work "Effective Software Testing: A Developer's Guide"[47].

C.3.1 Equivalence Partitioning

Equivalence Partitioning is a software testing technique used to reduce the number of test cases by dividing input data into partitions from which test cases can be derived, providing sufficient certainty about the correctness of the program. Although the number of possible program inputs is nearly infinite, certain groups of inputs will result in the same program behavior, regardless of the specific input value. In test terminology, the set of inputs triggering the same behavior are equivalent and therefore one specific input value can be chosen to represent the entire partition.

To apply this technique, one can start by reviewing the specification and requirements of the software to identify the appropriate input data. The next step would involve separating the identified test data into equivalence partitions. These partitions should cover both valid and invalid input data to ensure that test cases can detect both correct behavior and errors. Finally, a representative value from each partition should be selected and the test cases should be developed using the value as input data.

For example, consider having a simple function that should register a user if an accepted username is provided. The username has only one criterion to make it valid, and that is that it is within a certain length, say between 8-14 characters. This means that the test case has three equivalent partitions:

- Invalid: username less than 8 characters long
- Valid: username between 8 and 14 characters long
- Invalid: username more than 14 characters long

So, in this simple case, there are only three different cases that need to be derived.

C.3.2 Boundary Value Analysis

Boundary Value Analysis focuses on the values at the boundaries of the input domains. The rationale behind this approach is that errors are more likely to occur at the boundaries of input ranges rather than in the center of the input range. Boundaries can be defined as the place where the program suddenly changes its behavior, often lying in between partition classes. Whenever there is a boundary, two points should be tested - one belonging to each partition. To explore boundaries it is recommended to look at all the partitions and think of inputs between them.

In order to apply this technique the partition classes should be identified. Once this is done the boundary values can be identified by selecting consecutive values that trigger the behavioral change between the classes. Finally, test cases using boundary values as inputs should be developed.

Continuing on the example provided in the Equivalence Partitioning section, there are two places where the function changes its behavior and inputs cross the partition classes: at 8 and 15 characters. The values from both sides of the boundary of these changing points should be considered. Therefore, the following test cases should be considered:

- Invalid: Username with 7 characters
- Valid: Username with 8 characters
- Valid: Username with 14 characters
- Invalid: Username with 15 characters

C.3.3 Code coverage

Code-based testing can utilize code coverage criteria to gain confidence that the program works as expected. There exist different types of code coverage that should be considered when designing test cases, in order to augment the test suite.

Line coverage measures the extent to which the source code of a program is executed when a test suite runs. It represents the percentage of individual lines of code that are executed. If a test touches a line of code in any way, that line can be counted as covered.

Branch Coverage considers how the program behaves differently based on the evaluation of branching instructions like "if," "for," and "while" statements. A branch represents a distinct path in the execution flow, stemming from decisions. For example, an "if" statement can be evaluated as either true or false, which will open up two distinct branches. To reach full branch coverage, each possible path in the control flow of the program should be executed when running the test suite.

Condition Coverage considers each condition in a branch statement. For example, an "if" statement can consist of two individual conditions (if a AND b) and both need to be evaluated to be true for the entire statement to be evaluated to true. To reach condition coverage, the test suite should exercise each of those individual conditions being evaluated to true and false at least once.

To reach full **Path Coverage** all the possible paths of execution of the program should be covered. This means that every possible combination of conditions and loops in the code has been evaluated by the test suite. Ideally, this is the strongest criterion, but it can be hard and expensive to achieve since the number of test cases needed to cover all possible combinations rapidly increases with the number of conditions and loops in the code.

C.4 Test Optimization

One approach to reduce testing costs is to use different test case optimization techniques. Three widely accepted strategies are Test Case Selection, Test Case Minimization, and Test Case Prioritization. The first refers to choosing an appropriate subset of the test suite based on knowledge about the software. The second aims to increase efficiency by removing redundant tests and shrinking the test suite to a minimal subset that still reaches the desired adequacy criterion. Test case prioritization does not reduce the test suite compared to the two mentioned. Instead, the test suite is ordered so that the most important tests are executed first. In this way, critical errors are detected earlier, which optimizes time since it is possible to start addressing faults before the whole suite is executed. Meanwhile, if the test execution is abrupt, the most valuable tests have a higher chance of being run. [48]

C.5 Continuous Integration

Continuous Integration (CI) is a solution to automate the builds of a software project upon every commit. The main goal is to ensure the health of the software early in

the development lifecycle. A continuous integration pipeline can consist of various components, including compilation, rebuilding the database, running tests, inspections, and feedback mechanisms. In the context of software testing, it is common to integrate tests into the CI pipeline to automate the execution of tests. One benefit of CI is that this automated test contributes to greater confidence as well as reduces repetitive manual work. To achieve this, a build script needs to be shared in the version control system that instructs what tests should run on every build. GitHub Actions [12] is a feature that among other functionalities facilitates the use of build scripts in GitHub, by providing a solution to write and execute them.

While continuous integration facilitates testing, it is also a powerful tool for ensuring code quality. For example, static analysis can be introduced in the build script, ensuring code inspections on every commit. The book [49] highlights CI to be a "centerpiece for quality". It is the mentioned book that serves as the main source of knowledge for the stated information about CI. The ISO/IEC/IEEE standard highlights the usage of CI when describing automated tests.

C.6 Continuous Delivery

Continuous Delivery (CD) is an extension of Continuous Integration, still alleviating the process of automated testing. CD aims to ensure that the software is reliably released at any time, by automatically deploying code changes after the build stage. However, the deployment still needs approval before release and is not fully automated. Automatically deploying software upon every code change is called Continuous Deployment. [50]

TeamCity [13] is a software platform that facilitates workflows of CI/CD. In terms of CD, TeamCity enables simply deploying software from the version control system with one click. It is also possible to configure software tests to run on this development.

C.7 Human aspects related to testing

MohamadSaleh and Alzahrani [38] highlights that the majority of issues in the software development process are related to human factors. However, the research area has been given lesser attention compared to the technical field [51]. Behavioral Software Engineering (BSE) is defined as the study of cognitive, behavioral, and social aspects of software engineering performed by individuals, groups, or organizations [51]. The research in the area encompasses individual and organizational concepts such as motivation, communication, cognitive biases, and organizational culture. BSE is a growing area of research, but the existing research is unbalanced. BSE concepts have been applied to a limited number of Software Engineering areas and are not frequently connected to a specific phase of the Software development process. One of the Software Engineering areas that has been heavily underrepresented in BSE research is Software Testing, with around 1 % being connected to this area of knowledge [51]. Since software testing is a social-intensive activity [25], human aspects should not be neglected as a critical part of the testing process. Cognitive

biases are a phenomenon in the human aspects scene, which heavily affects the process of software engineering and thereby software testing. The next section outlines fundamental knowledge about cognitive biases and how they relate to software engineering. After covering cognitive biases, another human aspect is explained in relation to software testing; Motivation.

C.7.1 Cognitive Biases

Cognitive biases are systematic deviations from optimal reasoning. They can be explained as recurring errors in thinking or patterns of bad judgment [3]. This is a universal phenomenon observable in different social contexts. Cognitive biases explain many common software engineering problems in diverse areas including design, testing, requirements engineering, project management, etc. While there is no definitive list, over 200 cognitive biases have been identified in psychology, sociology, and management research. The following section describes some of the most well-known types of cognitive biases and their implications in the area of software Testing. The concepts explained are based on the work of R.Mohanani et al.[3], a systematic literature review of Cognitive biases in the area of Software Engineering.

Confirmation bias is the tendency to pay more attention to information that agrees with perceptions. In the area of Software testing, confirmation bias can explain the tendency of software testers to design and run tests that confirm the expected execution of the program rather than ones that could reveal failures. During debugging, confirmation bias sometimes leads programmers to misidentify the reasons for program failure.

Optimism bias is the tendency to produce unrealistically optimistic estimates, judgments, and predictions. This bias can contribute to heavily underestimating the time needed to write tests during the software development process.

Anchoring and adjustment is a common heuristic in which one makes estimates by adjusting an initial value called an anchor. **Anchoring bias** is the tendency to stick too closely to the anchor. This bias can explain why developers tend to re-use existing queries rather than write new ones even though the existing queries may not be the best solution for the new situation. This phenomenon can lead to errors in the anchors propagating to the new artifacts. In the context of software testing, anchoring bias can explain why developers may re-use tests written for similar code instead of writing an entirely new test.

Availability bias is the tendency for easy-to-recall information to unduly influence preconceptions or judgments. Availability bias can also manifest in project-based organizations when decisions are based on information that is easy to recall or in the absence of knowledge. Software professionals tend to rely on their experiences or prior knowledge to seek information, ignoring unfamiliar and less-used keywords and locations. Availability bias is associated with the over-representation of memorable code features and certain controversies as preferring a familiar but less suitable programming language. In the context of Software Testing, availability bias may affect decisions made about the testing process and testing environment. For example, the decisions about what tools or techniques to use may be based on a lack of knowledge

about the knowledge area going for the easy-to-find solutions.

Overconfidence bias is the tendency to overestimate one's skills and abilities. In the context of Software Testing, this bias can explain why some developers may consider testing unnecessary and heavily under-prioritize this activity. Developers may feel so confident about their code that they may decide that some or no testing at all is good enough.

Adjustment bias can lead an individual to persevere with established or familiar opinions despite the presence of superior information, arguments, or conditions. In software testing, this could take the form of not changing to better testing tools or techniques because of comfort with the old solution.

Representativeness bias is the tendency to make a judgment by fitting an object into a stereotype or model based on a few properties. Due to representativeness people expect to obtain results that are considered representative or typical. This may lead to problems during the software testing phase of a product. Consider a developer who has to decide whether a specific test case should be eliminated or not. Such a decision depends on whether the specific test case is considered representative of the entire population of test cases that produce errors. This may explain why test cases that produce errors may be overlooked which leads to an increase in software defect density.

C.7.2 Motivation

The concept of motivation has been given multiple definitions across a variety of research areas. Work motivation has been referred to as the desire to work, signaled by the individual's engagement, focus, and attitudes towards the work [52]. According to Hackman's [53], work motivation refers to being engaged in one's work because of the positive internal feelings that are generated by performing well. Motivation is also defined in the Goal Setting Theory [41], as the willingness to strive for the goals of a particular organization. According to this theory, four elements represent motivated behavior: Direction - as the direct attention and action; Effort - as the amount of effort mobilized in proportion to the perceived requirements of the goal or task; Persistence - as the directed effort extended over time and Strategy Development - as the development of strategies or action plans for attaining one's goals.

Another theory, the "Motivation-Hygiene Theory" [54] classifies motivational factors as either extrinsic or intrinsic. Extrinsic motivation means the activity is a means to achieve a determined goal or desired result, for example, material gains or a promotion. While intrinsic motivation means the reward lies in the action itself. According to Steers [55], if it was possible to synthesize the different concepts of motivation they would all have a common characteristic: they are all primarily concerned with factors or events that energize, channel and sustain human behavior over time.

In the context of Software Engineering, motivation has been reported to have the single largest impact on productivity and software quality management, but it is still facing the challenge of being undermined [39]. In Software Testing, low motivation can lead to poor testing and overlooking of software defects [40]. Shah *et*

al. [56] concluded that the quality of testing is affected by testers' motivation and appreciation of testing efforts. As Fraser and Straubinger [26] highlighted in their paper "A Survey on What Developers Think About Testing", nearly 60 % of the participants would test more if they were better recognized. Recognition has been conceptualized as a form of constructive and genuine feedback that acknowledges individuals and their personal expertise and contributions. It is seen as a return on an employee's effort, dedication, and results [57].

C.8 Code Quality

Quality assurance and testing are closely interrelated, where testing is a method to perform quality control and thereby facilitates increasing the code quality [35]. Testing is in return benefited from software quality activities since higher code quality reduces testing costs [38]. This is mirrored in the study [32] where the authors highlight how poor quality causes extra work in testing activities. Toroi *et al.* [29] underscore the importance of continuous improvement of the software test process since it streamlines the code quality, which is claimed to be an important factor for competitiveness in the market. Among others, some key aspects for achieving high code quality are adhering to code standards, principles and design patterns, reducing complexity, and maintaining the code over time. Depending on the context, different guidelines are suitable to achieve high code quality. For example, if performing object-oriented programming, the SOLID Design Principles are widely recommended. The SOLID principles are presented in a lightweight way in a blog post [58] by Samuel Oloruntoba. Hassan and Singh [59] conducted a study where they applied the SOLID principles to a software product, compared it to not following the principles, and found that they increased code quality significantly.

Pair programming is a technique where two developers work together on one computer on the same programming task. Williams *et al.* [37] demonstrate that this is not only a technique that is often evaluated as enjoyable, rather it also ensures a higher quality of code in a shorter time compared to independent programming, no matter the expertise level.

There exist various ways to measure code quality from different views. One common way is to use metrics generated from various software tools. Following, some broadly accepted and commonly used metrics are presented. There exist variations on how to calculate the metrics, and below are the definitions for this study.

Code smells are signals of issues in the code, which do not cause any errors. These can lead to trouble anyhow since they limit the codebase's maintainability, readability, and extensibility. Often, code smells indicate a deeper issue in software design, but they can also be a syntactical smell that prohibits the understandability of the code.

Cyclomatic complexity refers to the number of linearly independent paths there is in a function. Whenever the control flow of a function divides, the cyclomatic complexity is increased by one. For example, the cyclomatic complexity of a function that consists of an conditional construct (if-else) is two.

Cognitive complexity refers to how difficult it is to understand the code's paths

from a human perspective. The metric increases with nested blocks and complex operators.

D

Examples

D.1 Exit Criteria

- All test cases must be executed, with a minimum of 95% passing.
- All high-priority issues identified must be resolved, and medium-priority issues must either be resolved or have a planned resolution documented.
- The test coverage must meet or exceed the agreed threshold of 90%.
- The software's performance must align with the specified performance benchmarks (system uptime of 99.9%), confirming that it can handle the expected load and stress conditions.
- Documentation of the testing process, including test results, bug reports, and quality metrics, must be completed and reviewed.

D.2 System Requirements for an E-commerce System

Functional Requirements:

- **Registration:** Users can register a new account by providing the required information such as name, address, phone number, email, password etc.
- **Product Management:** Administrators can add, update or remove products.
- **Search and Filtering:** Users can search for products using keywords or filter products based on characteristics such as brand, price, color etc.
- **Shopping cart:** Users can add items to their shopping cart, edit quantities or remove items.
- **Payment:** The system should facilitated payment through integration with multiple payment services such as credit card processing and Klarna.
- **Order Management:** User can view their order history and track their order status.
- **Notifications:** Users receive notifications about order status, promotions and other relevant information via email or SMS.

Non-Functional Requirements:

- **Scalability:** The system should be scalable to adapt to growth in the number of users, products and transaction volumes.
- **Reliability:** The system should have an uptime of at least 99,9 %.

- **Usability:** The user interface should be intuitive and accessible, supporting various devices and screen sizes.
- **Security:** The system should comply with data protection regulations and follow security mechanisms such as encryption and authentication.
- **Performance:** The system should be able to handle a high number of simultaneous users and transactions without degradation of performance.

D.3 High-level test case

Objective: Test positive number addition functionality **Steps:**

- Number A is typed in the first field
- Number B is typed in the second field.
- The "Calculate" button is clicked.

Expected Results:

- The Sum of A and B appears on screen.

D.4 Code Review Guide

- **Understand the Specified Functionality:**
 - Ensure the submitted code meets all the specified requirements and delivers the expected functionality.
- **Code Correctness and Quality:**
 - Check that the code includes passing unit tests which cover a range of scenarios, including edge cases.
 - Ensure the code adheres to the project's coding standards and best practices.
 - Review for logical correctness, algorithmic efficiency, and simplicity.
- **Documentation and Readability:**
 - Confirm that the code is well-documented, including clear comments, function descriptions, and inline comments where necessary.
 - Ensure the code is readable and maintainable, with a logical structure and consistent formatting.
- **Static Code Analysis:**
 - Ensure the code passes static code analysis with no critical issues.
 - Check for good maintainability ratings and absence of new code smells or technical debt.
- **Merge Readiness:**
 - Confirm there are no merge conflicts with the base branch, ensuring a smooth integration process.
- **Error Handling:**
 - Check that the code robustly handles errors and exceptions, providing clear, user-friendly error messages or logging where appropriate.
- **Extensibility and Scalability:**
 - Ensure the code is designed to allow for future extensions, modifications, and enhancements without significant rework.

- Assess whether the code follows principles that support scalability, such as modularity and loose coupling.
- **Security Aspects:**
 - Examine the code for potential security vulnerabilities, ensuring that it adheres to industry-standard security practices.
 - Check for the proper implementation of data validation, authentication, and authorization mechanisms.

E

Changes done to the original framework

The additions are marked with green. The deletions are marked with red. Changes such as reformulations are marked with orange.

Axis	No Implementation	Partial Implementation	Full Implementation
Testing knowledge	Limited	High-level understanding, not maintained	Continuously shared and maintained within the organization
Plan definition	No plan	Informal plan	Formal Plan. The plan is continuously maintained and evaluated
Affected test levels	No testing	Deliberate use of test levels. Mainly unit testing, some integration and system testing	Comprehensive unit, integration and system tests and higher level tests
Definition of test cases	No definition of test cases	High-level definition of test cases	Fully specified test cases
Test activities	No testing	Static or dynamic tests. Some testing techniques applied	Static and dynamic tests combined. Carefully selected testing techniques

E. Changes done to the original framework

Traceability	No traceability	Partial traceability	Full traceability
Test environment	No specific testing environment	Managed and controlled environment	Testing in a suitable environment
Testing tools	Non-specific tools	Specific tools for monitoring and executing tests	Extensive process automation
Code quality	Not considered or evaluated	Introduced guidelines	Full codebase adhere to guidelines
CI/CD pipeline	No tests included	Includes static and dynamic tests	Optimized tests
Feedback	No reports	Some internal and/or external defect reports	Extensive internal and external defect reports. Progress and process reports and activities
Developer motivation	No efforts have been made	Activities to enhance testing motivation have been introduced	Developers are motivated and recognized for testing activities

Table E.1: Color coded axis diagnostic matrix highlighting the revisions of this study.

Axis	Improvement activities
Testing knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include basic testing principles as well as the organizational approach regarding testing in the onboarding process • Provide simple resources to achieve fundamental testing knowledge • Emphasize unit testing • Clarify advantages of software testing

<p>Plan definition</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Answer the questions: What do we test? What do we not test? And why do we do it? When do we test? Where do we test? • Define the general approach to testing • Define and communicate roles and responsibilities for testing activities. Assign someone responsible for the software testing • Integrate and coordinate testing activities with the development lifecycle • Define product requirements • Define exit criteria • Generate a high-level test schedule. When starts each test, when it ends and the most important milestones
<p>Affected test levels</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analyze the available test objects from the unit, integration and system-level test perspectives • Identify the features to be tested from the previously analyzed test objects, as well as the conditions under which they will be tested • A rule of thumb is to focus the density of tests in the order of the test pyramid, with most tests in the lower levels
<p>Definition of test cases</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agree on a standard format for test case specification • Create high-level test cases. A checklist is often recommended as a first approximation
<p>Test activities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform static review tests, e.g., code reviews or inspections, walkthroughs, algorithm analysis and functional documentation reviews • Perform exploratory dynamic tests manually • Consider basic testing techniques such as Regression testing and Sanity testing

E. Changes done to the original framework

Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Maintain traceability between test objects and test cases
Test environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Build a test environment outside of the development and production environment• Prepare it with shared test data, where possible, that is similar to production data• Integrate triggering tests in the CI/CD pipeline
Testing tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Incorporate requirements and incident monitoring tools. As a first approximation, they can be carried in a spreadsheet, but it is advisable to use specific tools for this type of task• Incorporate test execution tools that allow them to be automated• Apply tools supporting unit testing
Code quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Chose code standard(s) to follow and establish a routine for staying updated with the guidelines (suggestion: workshop once a year)• Introduce automated tools for assessing code quality• Integrate the code quality aspects to code reviews• Communicate and educate the importance of modular code• Pair programming is encouraged• Comment the code
CI/CD pipeline	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Set up a pre-commit command that runs formatting and simple tests• Create a build script in the repository that states which set of tests should be run on every commit/push. Update the chosen set regularly• Integrate static code analysis tools for performing code quality checks• Create a build script for the deployment including what tests to run at this stage

Feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generate reports of internal defects. The idea is to communicate the quality level of the product under test. It is suggested to keep a count of the test cases executed, the result obtained and the defects reported once the derived adjustments have been made. It is also important to be able to estimate the resources / hours used to carry out this task • Establish metrics, such as code coverage, testing time, and number of failures • Integrate tools for extracting the metrics • Gather feedback from users • Keep a count of the test cases executed, the results obtained, and the defects reported
Developer motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the testing status at the company • Combine testing responsibilities with development activities • Ensure a variety of engaging and challenging tasks • Encourage a good relationship with management and colleagues • Set aside time destined for only testing activities • Ensure the testing environment holds a high quality • Provide a clear testing strategy to follow • Provide clear test examples to follow

Table E.2: Color coded evolution matrix from No Implementation level, highlighting the revisions of this study.

Axis	Improvement activities
Testing knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide courses in testing, with the possibility to advance in expertise level • Educate about cognitive biases that affect testing • Ensure fundamental testing skills before employment • Provide an opportunity to share knowledge with colleagues

E. Changes done to the original framework

Plan definition	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Document the plan, either in a specific tool or spreadsheet, and distribute it to the development team and stakeholders• Integrate and coordinate testing activities with development lifecycle activities• Make an estimated time budget required to carry out the test activities and add buffer time for testing activities• Generate a calendar with specific dates or in the context of each iteration• Estimate people and resources to carry out the planned activities. If possible, make a tentative assignment• Decide specialized testing needs at the company• Create opportunities for participatory decision-making• Hold retrospective meetings destined to maintain and evaluate the chosen testing process• Comprehend feedback from testing activities to fine-tune the testing plan• Follow up if product requirements have been fulfilled
Affected test levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Analyze the available integration and higher-level test objects, such as acceptance tests• Study the need for tests at specialized levels such as Installation tests• Identify the features to be tested in the different levels• Define and prioritize the conditions for each level while maintaining, as far as possible, traceability with the previous objects
Definition of test cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Choose appropriate test specification technique(s) to generate test cases• Utilize debasing techniques such as playing the devil's advocate• Generate test cases identifying: the possible input data, the execution conditions, and the expected results• Prioritize them based on the features to be tested• Document the fully specified test cases for follow-up

E. Changes done to the original framework

Test activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform static analysis tests guided by tools such as source code analysis (examples are given in the Code Quality axis), model checking and business process simulation • Automate dynamic tests • Consider more advanced testing techniques such as Search-based testing, Property-based testing, Mutation testing • Optimize tests
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add traceability between requirements and the test objects and test cases • Determine the coverage of the tests • Introduce test management tools
Test environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include in the test environment: test harness, service virtualization, simulators, and other necessary infrastructure elements • Prepare test data from production data and keep it up to date. The result should be an environment as similar to the productive environment within the possibilities and restrictions of the business • Mock external dependencies as often as possible for lower-level tests
Testing tools	<p>Incorporate tools for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • test management and test products • test design and implementation, to create maintainable work products, including test cases, test procedures, and test data • execution and registration of tests • performance measurement and dynamic analysis • specialized testing needs such as security tests, portability, and accessibility

Code quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do a full scan of the code base and fix existing code quality issues. This could be a good opportunity for someone with lower domain expertise or experience at the company to familiarize themselves with the code base (e.g., a summer job or a project for a new employee) • The code quality of every new change should be evaluated to meet the code quality guidelines
CI/CD pipeline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prioritize the order of the test cases in the build scripts • Perform risk assessment and run the critical first • Examine the different tests to not cover redundant tests • Ensure to not run the same tests in several build scripts if not needed
Feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generate progress reports to evaluate the process of the testing and track associated activities • Prepare defect reports to communicate the testing process and product quality • Allow interested parties to provide feedback about the quality achieved and priorities for future releases
Developer motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduce ways to provide positive feedback when discovering faults • Ensure active influence in decisions concerning the testing process • Make use of code quality metrics • Adopt pair programming practices

Table E.3: Color coded evolution matrix from Partial Implementation level, highlighting the revisions of this study.